

Improvement of auditing activities by combining theory, methodology and technologies

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ABSTRACT. This article examines how the integration of theory, methodology, and technology can change auditing practice and improve audit quality. It shows how they improve the quality and effectiveness of joint audits. The interaction between theoretical frameworks, methodological approaches and advanced technologies leads to more effective risk assessment and decision-making in audit practice. Also, as a result of the development of corporate accountability in global practice, the role of the audit has fundamentally changed, and it has shown the need to implement the "audit trinity" that increases the reliability of financial reports, including external and internal audit, audit committee.

In the context of globalization, rapid development and liberalization of the economy in Uzbekistan, acceleration of integration into the world financial market, further development of the capital market and the digital economy, and the introduction of modern corporate governance principles are among the most important priorities. The scientific significance of the research results in this article is explained by the fact that the theoretical and organizational-methodical aspects of the improvement of the audit by combining theory, methodology and technologies serve to carry out scientific developments aimed at improving the regulatory and legal documents in the field of auditor activity based on the international practical experience.

Key words: audit, theory, methodology, technology, risk, auditors, financial reporting, corporate governance, legislation, standards.

INTRODUCTION

Today, auditing activities are developing with the integration of advanced **theories, methodologies and technological** innovations. As companies grow more complex and global, robust audit processes are essential to ensure financial integrity and transparency. This evolution not only improves audit accuracy, but also builds trust among stakeholders.

Audit activity is based on several theoretical foundations that shape its practice. Agency theory is essential for understanding the relationship between principals such as shareholders and agents such as company managers [9]. This theory suggests the need for auditing to reduce information asymmetry and ensure that agents act in the best interests of principals. By independently evaluating financial statements, an audit helps bridge the gap between these parties and ensures transparency.

Stakeholder theory expands the focus beyond shareholders to include all parties affected by a company's actions. This perspective emphasizes the auditor's responsibility to consider various stakeholders, including employees, customers, and society. In this way, an audit helps to understand a company's impact and sustainability holistically, aligning financial reporting with broader societal demands.

Institutional theory monitors how external pressures, such as regulatory requirements and industry norms, shape audit processes. This framework emphasizes the importance of consistency and alignment in maintaining audit quality. As regulations evolve, auditors must update their practices to meet new standards so that auditing remains a reliable tool for financial control.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS

Some aspects of this issue have been solved in the scientific works of foreign scientists A.Arens, M.Beasley, R.Elder [4], Cohen J.R. [9], R.Adams [5], V.P.Suys [10], A.A.Terekhov [17], A.D.Sheremet [19] and others, who conducted research on the improvement of technologies for the scientific-theoretical and methodological support of audit activity.

Scientific-methodical and practical aspects of audit are partially reflected in the scientific works of Uzbek economists K.B.Akhmedjanov [6], A.Z.Avlokulov [7], O.O.Barakaev [8], R.D.Dusmuratov [11], A.K.Ibragimov [12], A.A.Karimov [13], M.M.Tulakhujayeva [18], B.A.Khasanov [15], B.Q.Khamdamov [16].

Audit research methodologies are evolving to adapt to the changing business landscape and emerging challenges. Different methodologies are used to examine different aspects of an audit. Qualitative approaches such as case studies and interviews are useful for exploring complex, contextual issues. These methods allow

researchers to understand nuanced dynamics in audit practice, such as auditor-client interactions or the influence of organizational culture on audit outcomes.

Quantitative methodologies provide a systematic approach to examining audit events. Methods such as surveys and experiments allow researchers to analyze models across larger samples and provide generalizable findings that can inform auditing standards. For example, a survey can evaluate the effectiveness of different audit strategies in detecting financial misstatements, and experiments can examine the effects of auditor training programs on performance. Statistical analysis ensures rigor and objectivity in the research process, increases the reliability of findings.

Mixed method studies combining qualitative and quantitative methods are finding their place in audit research. This approach leverages the strengths of both methodologies to provide a comprehensive review of audit issues. By combining qualitative insights with quantitative data, researchers can develop a richer understanding of the complex audit environment. For example, a mixed methods study might begin with qualitative interviews to identify key themes, followed by a quantitative survey to measure their prevalence and importance.

Statistical methods are important in audit analysis and provide auditors with tools to verify financial information. These methods allow auditors to detect anomalies, assess risks, and ensure the accuracy of financial statements. Regression analysis allows auditors to examine relationships between variables and predict potential outcomes. By using regression models, auditors can identify patterns that may indicate unusual financial activity, such as revenue manipulation or expense misclassification.

Sampling is another important statistical method of auditing. Given the impracticality of auditing every transaction, auditors rely on sampling to draw conclusions about the population based on a subset of the data. Techniques such as stratified sampling ensure that selection is helpful and reduce the risk of bias. By carefully selecting audits, auditors can focus on high-risk areas and increase audit efficiency and effectiveness.

Data analysis tools such as the International Data Encryption Algorithm (IDEA) and the Access Control List (ACL) have revolutionized the use of statistical methods in auditing. These tools automate data processing and analysis, enabling real-time understanding of financial transactions. By using machine learning algorithms, auditors can identify patterns and trends that are not immediately apparent using traditional methods. This increases the auditor's ability to detect fraud and provides a deeper understanding of the organization's financial position.

DISCUSSION

Behavioral aspects of auditing and effective risk assessment models can be achieved through audit research methodologies. This shapes the interactions and dynamics between auditors and clients. Understanding these aspects provides insight into how audit processes evolve and the factors that influence audit outcomes. Auditor judgments and decisions are influenced by cognitive biases that may affect audit quality. A confirmation bias, for example, can lead auditors to look for evidence that supports their initial view, ignoring conflicting evidence. Training programs aimed at raising awareness of such misconceptions can help mitigate their effects and promote objective audit evaluation.

The auditor-client relationship has a significant impact on audit quality. While strong, collaborative relationships can facilitate communication and access to information, they can also be risky. Too closeness threats can arise when auditors have close relationships with clients, compromising their independence. Implementing a rotation policy for audit teams can reduce these risks by providing fresh perspectives and maintaining professional skepticism.

Effective risk assessment models are important in auditing because companies operate in a complex environment. These models provide systematic approaches for identifying, evaluating, and prioritizing risks that may affect financial statements. The Committee of Sponsoring Organizations (COSO Enterprise Risk Management) system offers a comprehensive method of internal and external risk assessment [8]. This framework encourages auditors to consider a wide range of risk factors, from market volatility to operational disruptions.

Predictive analytics play a role in predicting potential financial anomalies. Using historical data and advanced algorithms, auditors can identify patterns that indicate future risks. This proactive approach allows organizations to address potential issues before they occur. The integration of technology in risk assessment models increases accuracy and enables real-time monitoring of risk factors, providing auditors with timely insights.

RESULTS

Integrating audit theory, methodology and technology through effective risk assessment models leads to an increase in audit quality indicators (AQI). AQI are indicators for evaluating the auditor's performance and the reliability of financial statements [3]. One common AQI is the amount of auditor-client meetings, which indicates the level of identification and understanding of the client's transactions.

Regular interactions often lead to deeper investigations that allow for timely problem identification and resolution.

Another important AQI is adherence to professional standards and guidelines. Compliance with established auditing standards, such as those established by the International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB), ensures consistency and reliability in auditing practices [2; 14]. The use of advanced data analytics tools to examine large amounts of financial data serves as an AQI that indicates an auditor's propensity to use technology to improve audit quality. By monitoring these indicators, audit organizations can identify areas for improvement and maintain high standards of practice.

CONCLUSION

Audit theory and methodology are improved by integrating technologies, and an institutional approach to comprehensive auditing is achieved. The integration of technology into audit procedures will transform the industry and increase efficiency and effectiveness. Artificial intelligence (AI) automates routine tasks and allows auditors to focus on complex analyses. AI-based tools quickly process large amounts of data and detect violations that may be missed by mechanical methods. This speeds up the audit process and increases the accuracy of conclusions.

Blockchain technology offers the potential for auditing by providing an immutable balance of transactions that can be easily verified. With blockchain, auditors can trace the origin of financial transactions with transparency, which reduces the risk of fraud. In addition, cloud computing facilitates the storage and analysis of large data sets, allowing auditors to access and analyze data in real time. These technological advances are reshaping the audit landscape, creating opportunities for innovation and improvement.

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